

THE BERLIN ETHICS CERTIFICATE: CONCEPTUALIZING INTERDISCIPLINARITY AS A CORE BUILDING BLOCK OF ETHICS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

To address the need for more responsible research and innovation, there is a growing call to integrate ethics education across the science and engineering curriculum. Accordingly, ethics education must not be limited to the avoidance of scientific misconduct but rather be oriented toward addressing the complexity of planetary challenges and realizing social good. Designing curricula to accommodate the ambition of integrated ethics, however, remains a great institutional and epistemic challenge. In this paper, we introduce the *Berlin Ethics Certificate* (BEC) at the Technical University of Berlin, to demonstrate how this challenge can be addressed by using interdisciplinarity as a core building block of integrated ethics education. The BEC's unique approach to ethics education enables the positioning of ethical issues in all study programs within the university by designing future-oriented interdisciplinary courses open to all students, be they from the humanities, natural or engineering sciences. The paper outlines the BEC's conceptualization of interdisciplinarity, ultimately arguing that interdisciplinary ethics education must be built upon the epistemic practice of situating knowledge. Methodologically, we show how the BEC approaches integrated ethics education through three iterative steps: 1) situating disciplinary knowledge in relation to other forms of knowledge, values and experiences (by focusing on multidisciplinary learning experiences), 2) establishing a common epistemic practice of collaboration (by focusing on interdisciplinary learning experiences), and 3) actively engaging with non-academic stakeholders to create responsible technology and take ethical action beyond the university (by focusing on transdisciplinary learning experiences). Examples of how the BEC implements this methodology are shown, which may serve as suggestions of best practices in integrated ethics education.

1 INTRODUCTION

In face of the many planetary-scale crises faced by societies today, dealing with ethics and figuring out how to shape responsible futures is becoming an urgent matter. We are arguably more dependent on science and technology than ever before, and thus also more vulnerable to associated risks. To meet the demand of these challenges, teaching ethics to engineers has become common practice, as ethical, social and environmental considerations have been widely recognized as critical for engineering, computer and data science education. In the European context, the call for responsible research and innovation has placed further emphasis on ethics education in the technical sciences to steer processes of technological development toward socially desirable effects and mitigate downstream harms.

However, in the growing body of research on ethics in engineering education, there is considerable debate regarding proper course content and learning objectives, best teaching methods, and effectiveness of outcomes [1][2]. Most discussed is the question of how to best incorporate ethics into engineering education. The dominant paradigm, stemming from a lineage of professional and business ethics, has focused on the avoidance of individual scientific and moral misconduct (e.g., Responsible Conduct in Research in the US), and siloed modes of ethical reasoning taught in appendix “applied ethics” modules [3]. There is increasing recognition of the limitations of this paradigm, namely its failure to teach ethical reasoning skills beyond individual compliance and its subordination of ethics to dominant motives of technological progress and economic growth [1][3]. To address these limitations, there is a growing call to integrate ethics education across the science and engineering curriculum [2]. Accordingly, ethics education must not be limited to codes of conduct but rather be oriented towards addressing the complexity of current and future local to planetary-scale challenges and bringing about positive societal change. A key element of such an approach involves integrating ethical reflection across the curriculum so that ethical questions can be addressed from the perspective of many disciplines. Designing curricula to accommodate the ambition of integrated ethics, however, remains a great institutional and epistemic challenge, primarily due to the difficulty of cross-disciplinary activity.

In this paper, we present a response to this challenge in ethics education: the Technical University of Berlin’s newly established certificate program *Reflection and Responsibility—Berlin Ethics Certificate*. The certificate program integrates ethical reflection across all study programs by using interdisciplinarity as a core building block of ethics education. In section 2, we first outline the basic structure of the certificate and its setting at the Technical University of Berlin (TUB), where ethics and the humanities are granted a special status due to the history of the university. In section 3, we propose interdisciplinarity as a building block of integrated ethics education with the Berlin Ethics Certificate (BEC). In section 3.1, we conceptualize interdisciplinarity as an epistemic practice, focusing on the dynamics of knowledge production in interdisciplinary collaboration and the epistemic requirements for actors involved. In section 3.2., we argue that interdisciplinary collaboration must be

founded on the practice of situating knowledge, which allows for students to perceive their disciplinary and non-disciplinary knowledge as partial and gain an awareness of their values and moral intuitions, thereby enabling them to successfully enter a process of joint reflection. In section 3.3, we then show how this practice of situating knowledge is used by the BEC to ultimately generate socially responsible and epistemically robust knowledge. Finally, in section 4, we provide concrete examples from the BEC to demonstrate how integrated ethics education is implemented by focusing on multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary learning experiences.

2 THE BERLIN ETHICS CERTIFICATE AT TU BERLIN

Today, numerous German and international technical universities have humanities departments and offer affiliated study programs. However, the presence of different disciplinary cultures at the TUB is special in this respect, as it has had a humanities faculty since 1950. The reference to humanistic-oriented values through the humanities as well as a civil clause are special characteristics rooted in the TUB's historical responsibility accepted for the atrocities committed during the era of National Socialism in Germany.⁴ In line with this, the present mission statement states that “research and teaching in the natural, planning and engineering sciences are inextricably linked with the humanities and social sciences” [4]. According to its mission statement for teaching, academic education should “enable students to develop as individuals”. Furthermore, they should “learn to place their knowledge and actions within a broader historical, social, and cultural context and to reflect on the ethical consequences of their actions” [5]. With its focus on social and ethical responsibility on one hand, and interdisciplinary community building on the other, the BEC realizes these principles. Within the program, students are educated to take responsibility for the future by orienting their scientific and technological practices toward desirable visions for society and to practice interdisciplinary collaboration.

Reflection and Responsibility—Berlin Ethics Certificate offers students the opportunity to develop a specialization in ethics, science theory and technology reflection as a complement to their disciplinary studies. Students from all study programs, including the humanities, social, natural and engineering sciences, may volunteer to register for the certificate program, which is completed by attending courses of their choice offered by the BEC. The BEC was launched in 2021 and is coordinated by a working group of the *Berlin Ethics Lab* at TU Berlin and an interdisciplinary advisory board of the *Berlin University Alliance*.

⁴ Between 1933 and 1945, numerous Jewish scientists were expelled from the formerly *Technische Hochschule Berlin*, while its remaining researchers played an essential role in maintaining a network among science and military actors and participated in National Socialist armament research. Following the war, the partially destroyed university was reinaugurated in 1946 as *Technische Universität Berlin* by the British allies with a new humanistic orientation and educational mission, instantiated by the founding of the Faculty of Humanities in 1950.

Fig.1 Two-stage structure of the Berlin Ethics Certificate

The BEC's two-stage structure enables the acquisition of a foundational *Basic Certificate* and optional supplementary *Advanced Certificate*, whereby required credit points can be distributed over bachelor and master's degree programs and completed within the standard period of study [Fig. 1]. The qualification can be acquired via compulsory or elective courses, which upon completion are accredited within BEC "container modules". Corresponding courses are accredited based on their thematic and credit point conformity to BEC container modules and are primarily drawn from the existing rich curriculum of TU Berlin. In addition, supplementary interdisciplinary courses have been created, including a compulsory *Basic Module* for all participants of the BEC, which lays the

groundwork for ethical reflection on a personal level as well as for interdisciplinary cooperation.

3 INTERDISCIPLINARITY AS A BUILDING BLOCK FOR ETHICS EDUCATION

Although the question of how interdisciplinarity can contribute to ethics education is not new [6][7] and there is wide agreement that interdisciplinary collaboration is necessary for addressing real-world problems [8], there exist few examples of best practices. Before we explain in more detail how the BEC employs interdisciplinarity as a core building block, we want to outline the BEC's conceptualization of interdisciplinarity. This is important as concepts of interdisciplinarity in academic teaching and research vary due to a multitude of approaches, and reaching a uniform general definition seems difficult [9]. A common delineation, however, distinguishes interdisciplinarity as a form of synergistic interaction between disciplines rather than a mere combination of disciplines as in the case of multidisciplinary [7]. In the field of possible interaction between different disciplines, a rough distinction can be made between multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinarity. While these three kinds of interaction share the aspect of bringing together different forms of (disciplinary) knowledge, they differ in terms of how actors are involved in interactive processes and in which ways various forms of knowledge interact to respond to different problems.

3.1 The Berlin Ethics Certificate's conceptualization of interdisciplinarity

The BEC understands interdisciplinarity as a temporary, collaborative process of knowledge production, where diverse epistemic actors with different disciplinary

backgrounds come together in a common working environment by collaborating on project-based work. By bringing in their different expertise, namely their prior knowledge and disciplinary methods, actors enter a joint epistemic process, which unfolds in a milieu of reflection—a joint arena of thinking and reasoning [10]. A successful interdisciplinary process leads to an epistemic ascent (in the form of new knowledge or insights) through knowledge generation by knowledge integration. This contrasts with multidisciplinary, where no integration of knowledge takes place, and transdisciplinarity, where non-academic actors enter the joint process of knowledge production.

From an epistemological point of view, interdisciplinary knowledge production can be characterized by how the various actors are involved in the joint epistemic process of project work. Firstly, actors have only partial (disciplinary and non-disciplinary) knowledge and are ignorant in other domains relevant to the joint project and must therefore develop strategies to deal with limited knowledge as well as known and unknown unknowns (given their epistemic perspective). Secondly, epistemic actors must integrate bodies of knowledge from other disciplines into their own knowledge horizon and must therefore develop strategies to deal competently with knowledge without understanding it in depth. Thirdly, none of the epistemic actors involved in the process have total knowledge in the sense of being able to fully understand the initial knowledge basis of the project (such as initial assumptions or methods) as well as the emerging knowledge. Therefore, new strategies for collaborative testing and validation of emerging knowledge are needed.

Interdisciplinary collaboration places high demands on the design of the resulting milieu of reflection (based on the framework design and process design of the project) as well as on the persons participating in the joint process. As epistemic actors they must bring specific competencies and epistemic values including humility in recognition of the knowledge of others. This recognition of other modes of knowledge production presupposes a recognition of one's own epistemic boundaries, which is based on honest and clear communication of the limits of one's disciplinary knowledge, methods, and worldview (e.g. "here I am stuck", "here I am uncertain", "here I need help", "here I made a mistake"). Curiosity and openness towards other points of view and towards unknowns as well as an eagerness to learning from others are crucial for interdisciplinary collaboration. This, in turn, presupposes an agility to taking another perspective and a readiness for change. Furthermore, trust is necessary to rely epistemically on the expertise of others in areas where one might have none. Lastly, the willingness to share (knowledge, methods, failures) and ability to actively listen are also vital to the epistemic success of the joint process.

3.2 These demands clearly show that interdisciplinary collaboration does not come without the effort of those involved. To make this kind of project-based collaboration work successful and satisfying, specific education of the persons involved is needed. In addition, the process design should aim at targeted interventions to raise awareness and sensitivity towards

the above-mentioned prerequisites. Finally, of equal importance is the framework design, which implements a culture of interaction. Essential here is the fostering of values which trigger a positive and stimulating mutual learning environment, such as social and moral (non-epistemic) ones. Specifically, an interdisciplinary learning environment should foster treatment with dignity over disrespect; empowerment rather than intimidation; encouragement rather than discouragement; independence and personal responsibility instead of overdependence; recognition of differences instead of discrimination; and allowing for learning from mistakes instead of (public) shaming. Practices of situating knowledge

As the BEC's conceptualization of interdisciplinarity shows, a high degree of reflexivity on the part of all actors involved is required. Thus, to provide the foundation for interdisciplinary collaboration, BEC draws on epistemic practices of situating knowledge in multidisciplinary learning environments. Our approach is inspired by Donna Haraway's concept of *situated knowledge* [11], which expresses the fundamental conditionality of all scientific knowledge, by highlighting the social location of the researcher and the historical, political, and disciplinary constraints that condition the production of knowledge. Situated knowledges serve to create "a more adequate, richer, better account of a world, in order to live in it well and in critical, reflexive relation to our own as well as others' practices of domination and the unequal parts of privilege and oppression that make up all positions" (p. 579). Through learning that knowledge is always situated, students are prepared to engage in inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration to address ethical issues. Educational approaches of the BEC allow students to situate their knowledge in four respects, which exist in an iterative process and do not correspond to an explicit order.

Firstly, one's own disciplinary knowledge is situated within a broader academic knowledge framework. Students get an understanding of the scope and limitations of their respective disciplinary methods by being exposed to differing approaches. Examining the similarities and differences of their own disciplinary approach relative to others allows them to become aware of their epistemic blind spots and "disciplinary goggles", which frame how they address the world.

Secondly, one's own disciplinary knowledge is situated within one's broader non-academic knowledge stemming from their life experiences. Rather than leaving their life experiences "at the door" and engaging with topics on a purely intellectual or abstract basis, students are encouraged to understand their academic practice through the lens of their own personal and non-academic experiences.

Thirdly, one's own disciplinary knowledge is situated within one's personal values and moral intuitions. Students are encouraged to see their emotions, values, customs and background as a resource for collaborative practices. The emphasis on a holistic perspective on the self enables students to carry ethical reflection taught inside the classroom beyond their academic experience.

Lastly, one's own disciplinary knowledge is situated with respect to one's social positioning as means of gaining a reflexive awareness of power relations and their ethical consequences in process of knowledge production. In this sense ethics is approached from perspectives that account for the actual non-ideal conditions that inform our realities, including those of oppression and difference. Such a critical theory-informed approach to ethics is not only concerned with analyzing the impact of emerging technologies on society, but also affecting change.

Through these practices of situating knowledge, students explore resonance and reciprocity at the intersections of their knowledge opening up new lines of affinity and common ground while allowing for epistemic pluralism. In addition, community building, as a key aspect of the BEC program, is achieved by students gaining an awareness of the interdependencies amongst each other and their environment and developing a sense of collective responsibility for improving societal conditions. Situating knowledge in such a way prepares the ground for an interdisciplinary reflection of ethical issues in order to generate socially responsible and epistemically robust knowledge.

3.3 Interdisciplinarity for socially responsible and epistemically robust knowledge

Based on the practice of situating knowledge, the BEC employs interdisciplinarity as a core building block for integrated ethics education. Social and ethical responsibility and technology reflection are taught in interdisciplinary learning environments whereby students from engineering, science, the humanities and social science work together on common projects. Thereby, the BEC's ethics education goes beyond merely "ethics for engineers" so that ethical questions and problem framings can be sought simultaneously from many disciplinary perspectives. We concur that practicing ethics can be seen as "an inherently interdisciplinary endeavor" [6] (p. 259), ethical problems in society are multifaceted and arise from the intersection of different knowledge domains. Students of the BEC experience how knowledge is generated mutually through a guided collaboration of their respective disciplines, practices of disagreement and compromise, and exploring alternative perspectives. By this, interdisciplinary collaboration contributes to the generation of socially responsible and epistemically robust knowledge, with the aim of directing scientific and technological processes towards beneficial outcomes for society and the environment, as emphasised in approaches of technology assessment (TA) and responsible research and innovation (RRI) [12][13]. Accordingly, robust knowledge is crucial for effectively addressing the complex problems of the 21st century, including in the context of emerging technologies, which can no longer be adequately addressed by isolated disciplines. Robust knowledge stems from epistemic processes which bring together a multiplicity of disciplinary and societal perspectives, across many time scales and spatial contexts. Crucially, robust knowledge is not only about integrating diverse disciplinary knowledge, but also considering the social positions and power relations of the actors involved or affected, along with their diverse values and experiences, with the goal of protecting

and promoting human emancipation in the scientific process. In the following, we show how the BEC enables students from different disciplines to come together in an interdisciplinary learning environment, thereby demonstrating the BEC's approach to integrated ethics.

4 HOW INTERDISCIPLINARITY IS TURNED INTO A TEACHING CONCEPT: EXAMPLES FROM THE BERLIN ETHICS CERTIFICATE

The BEC implements integrated ethics education through three iterative steps: 1) situating disciplinary knowledge in relation to other forms of knowledge, values and experiences (by focusing on multidisciplinary learning experiences), 2) establishing a common epistemic practice of collaboration (by focusing on interdisciplinary learning experiences), and 3) actively engaging with non-academic stakeholders to create responsible technology and take ethical action beyond the university (by focusing on transdisciplinary learning experiences).

As mentioned in section 2, the BEC qualifications can be acquired via compulsory or elective courses that are open to all students of TU Berlin and can be accredited upon completion within the BEC modules. Corresponding courses are accredited based on their thematic and credit point conformity to the BEC modules. Due to the character of the interdisciplinary "container modules", the BEC allows students a high degree of freedom in the choice of course content. At the same time, the structure of the certificate (basic and advanced) reflects the close connection between ethics, epistemology and inter- and transdisciplinarity, as conceptualized by the BEC.

The BEC's mandatory module, "Reflection and Responsibility — Basic Module," lays the foundation for ethical reflection at the personal level through multidisciplinary learning experiences which focus on situating knowledge. The overall structure of this module includes a total of five workshops (corresponding to themes of responsibility, ethics, philosophy of science, inter- and transdisciplinarity), which provide the thematic and methodological foundation for all other modules (i.e. "Ethics and Social Responsibility", "Theory and Methods of Science", "Integrated Ethics — Transdisciplinary Technology Development") of the BEC [Fig. 1]. Drawing on their own disciplinary as well as everyday experiences, students learn to situate their knowledge within a multidisciplinary learning environment. For example, in the philosophy of science workshop, students are grouped by discipline and explore the epistemic possibilities and boundaries of their own disciplinary methods in relation to those of other disciplines. Over the course of the module, students are tasked with developing an ethical question on a self-elected topic, where the idea is that they reflect their own knowledge, values and experiences to critically engage with a relevant societal issue. Through the method of situating knowledge, the module ultimately teaches the relevance of individual and collective responsibility to epistemology, and interdisciplinarity to ethical reflection on real-world problems.

The course "Ethical and Social Challenges of Emerging Technologies: Automation, Robotics, AI" — which can be accredited under the container module "Ethics and

Social Responsibility" — serves as an example of an interdisciplinary learning experience. In interdisciplinary teams, students develop in-depth proposals for responsible technology design by establishing a common epistemic practice which progresses in a milieu of reflection. The selection of their own case study gives students the opportunity to seek personally and ethically relevant connections between technology, science, environment, society and each other. This bottom-up approach also allows students to think beyond mere technological problem solving and tech-solutionism by assessing technology in a wider socio-technical framework. Interdisciplinary methods are developed in joint workshops on systems thinking and framework analysis, value assessment, and critical design thinking. Ethics thereby is not taught as mere theory ready to be applied, but is actively experienced as an interdisciplinary epistemic practice, one that is tangible and practicable through project-based learning.

Finally, the BEC specialization module "Integrated Ethics — Transdisciplinary Technology Development", which is still under planning, aims at transdisciplinary learning by addressing real-world problems through action-oriented engagement with stakeholders. By exploring ethical questions in a practical project, students learn methods of participatory technology design and integrated technology assessment. They experience directly that technological futures can be shaped in cooperation with societal actors towards mutually desirable outcomes.

Based on the epistemic practice of situating knowledge, participating in the BEC enables students to trace a process from reflection to action, that is, to engage in processes of ethical reflection within multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary learning experiences, thereby making knowledge production more reflexive, responsible and robust.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

While there is a growing call to integrate ethics across engineering curricula and broaden ethical reflection beyond individual compliance, there is no standard curriculum or agreed upon methodology of how to do so. The Berlin Ethics Certificate presents a novel curriculum structure and epistemological approach for integrated ethics, which employs interdisciplinarity as a core driver of ethical reflection.

In this paper, we have argued that crucial to the integration of ethical reflection into science and technology education is the conceptualization of interdisciplinarity as an epistemic practice, which draws on situating knowledge. The epistemic practices of situating knowledge address the call for ethics education to be more emotionally engaging, critically reflective, grounded in real-life experience, and responsive to the complexity and inherent interdisciplinary nature of real-world problems. Situating one's disciplinary knowledge in relation to other disciplines, as well as one's personal experiences, values, and social positioning, allows one to engage in interdisciplinary joint reflection. In this joint process of interdisciplinary collaboration, new knowledge

is generated by the integration of partial perspectives and the common search for novel methodologies to test and validate emerging knowledge. Through the BEC's approach to ethics, which upholds the necessity of robust knowledge stemming from a diversity of standpoints, interdisciplinary collaboration is oriented toward taking ethical action. In this sense, students learn to associate ethics with broader societal engagement rather than the simple prevention of scientific misconduct. Through the BEC's emphasis on community building, the shared practice of ethics not only fosters mutual understanding in the disciplinary sense but also allows for students to experience collective responsibility for the future.

Beyond its theoretical contribution of understanding interdisciplinarity as an epistemic practice based on situating knowledge, this paper has outlined a new structural approach for integrating ethics across the curriculum. Rather than teaching "ethics for engineers", the BEC's structure allows for ethical problem framings to be investigated simultaneously by students from a range of disciplinary backgrounds. We have outlined several concrete examples and courses, which may serve as examples of best practice for interdisciplinary and integrated ethics education. Only when ethical reflection becomes integrated into the education of students dealing with science and technology, can we begin to address the complexity of the societal challenges we face.

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